

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Formaldehyde and Formic Acid by Bromamine-T in Acid Medium

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Kinetics of oxidation of formaldehyde and formic acid by bromamine-T (BAT) has been investigated in perchloric acid medium. The rate followed first order kinetics each in [BAT] and [S] with both the substrates. The rate was zero order in $[H^+]$ with HCHO and inverse first order in $[H^+]$ with HCOOH. Effects of added reaction products, variations in ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium have also been investigated in both cases. Mechanisms in conformity with the observed kinetics have been suggested. The rate constants for the rate limiting steps have been computed. The latter constants have been used to predict the rate constants for the variation of $[H^+]$ and [HCOOH].

As a part of our investigations with *N*-halogeno-*N*-metallo reagents¹⁻⁵ we report herein the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of formaldehyde and formic acid by bromamine-T (BAT), a source of positive bromine, in perchloric acid medium.

The redox reactions involving aldehydes and carboxylic acids are of interest both from pure chemical and industrial points of view. The oxidants so far used include $KMnO_4$, Co^{III} , Ag^{I} , Ce^{IV} and chloramine-T⁶.

Experimental

Bromamine-T was prepared by partial debromination of dibromamine-T¹¹ and the purity was checked by its spectra and iodometric estimation of the active bromine present in it. Aqueous stock solutions ($\sim 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) of BAT, formaldehyde and formic acid (Glaxo) were prepared and standardised. All other reagents employed were of AnalaR grade. Preliminary investigations showed that the ionic strength of the medium had no significant effect on the rate of reaction.

Kinetic studies were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions ($[HCHO \text{ or } HCOOH] \gg [BAT]$) in pyrex tubes. The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of a measured amount of BAT solution, pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to a mixture containing known amounts of substrate solution, $HClO_4$ and water, equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored by iodometric estimation of unreacted BAT at regular intervals of time at least for two half-lives. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed by the method of least-squares were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

The stoichiometries of the reactions were determined at different $[H^+]$ ($\sim 0.02-0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) by equilibrating varying ratios of [BAT] to [HCHO]

and [HCOOH] at 303 K for 24 h. Formic acid and CO_2 were identified as the products with formaldehyde and formic acid, respectively, by standard tests. *p*-Toluenesulphonamide (PTS), the reduced product of BAT, was detected by paper chromatography. It was further noticed that formic acid was not oxidised to CO_2 at $[HCOOH] < 0.003 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Under the conditions employed with formaldehyde, formic acid produced would be around $0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Hence it would not get oxidised further to CO_2 . The observed stoichiometries may be represented by equations (1) and (2).

Results

Kinetics of oxidations of formaldehyde and formic acid by BAT were investigated at several $[reactants]_0$. At constant $[HClO_4]$ with several fold excess of HCHO or HCOOH (at least by 5-10 times), plots of $\log [BAT]_0/[BAT]$ vs time were linear at least for two half-lives, and the pseudo-first order rate constants were unaffected by the changes in $[BAT]_0$ (Table 1), establishing the first order kinetics in [BAT] with both HCHO and HCOOH. At constant [BAT] and $[HClO_4]$, the rates increased with increase in $[HCHO]$ or $[HCOOH]$ and the $\log-\log$ plots of k_{obs} vs $[HCHO]$ and k_{obs} vs $[HCOOH]$ were linear with unit slopes indicating first order kinetics each in $[HCHO]$ and $[HCOOH]$. At constant $[HCHO]$ or $[HCOOH]$ and [BAT], the rate decreased with increase in $[H^+]$ with formic acid with an inverse first order dependence in $[H^+]$ and the rate was independent of $[H^+]$ with HCHO.

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR OXIDATION OF HCHO AND HCOOH BY BAT AT 303 K

[HCHO] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	[BAT] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[H^+]_{eff}^a$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	k_{obs} $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	[HCOOH] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	[BAT] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[H^+]_{eff}^a$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	k_{obs} $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
4.0	1.0	4.57	2.50	0.6	1.0	4.57	13.3
5.0	1.0	4.57	2.98	1.0	1.0	4.57	19.6
7.5	1.0	4.57	4.86	1.5	1.0	4.57	33.8
10.0	1.0	4.57	6.48	2.0	1.0	4.57	45.5
20.0	1.0	4.57	15.00	3.0	1.0	4.57	55.8
5.0	1.0	0.96	2.90	5.0	1.0	4.57	100.5
5.0	1.0	1.89	2.88	1.0	1.0	1.89	42.2
5.0	1.0	3.69	8.07	1.0	1.0	3.69	24.1
5.0	1.0	6.70	3.02	1.0	1.0	4.57	19.6
5.0	1.0	8.77	2.84	1.0	1.0	6.70	13.6
5.0	1.0	16.60	2.92	1.0	1.0	8.77	10.2
5.0	0.5	4.57	2.88	1.0	1.0	16.60	5.9
5.0	1.0	4.57	2.98	1.0	0.5	4.57	19.4
5.0	2.0	4.57	2.92	1.0	1.0	4.57	19.6
5.0	4.0	4.57	2.97	1.0	2.0	4.57	19.6

^aComputed from the equivalent conductances of aqueous HClO_4 .

Addition of the reaction products, PTS and Br^- , and change in the solvent composition by adding methanol had no significant effect on the rate in both cases. Activation parameters have been computed from the Arrhenius plots by measuring rates at different temperatures (Table 2).

TABLE 2

	E_a kJ mol^{-1}	$\log A$	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger $\text{Jk}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}
HCHO	106.8	14.9	104.3	40.0	92.2
HCOOH	85.5	11.9	82.5	-16.4	87.5

$$\frac{d[\text{BAT}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{HCOO}^-] [\text{BAT}]$$

$$= \frac{K_a k_1 [\text{HCOOH}] [\text{BAT}]}{[\text{H}^+]}$$
(3)

or

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_a k_1 [\text{HCOOH}]}{[\text{H}^+]} = k_1 [\text{HCOO}^-]$$
(4)

Discussion

Bromamine-T (RNBrNa), like chloramine-T^{1,12} and bromamine-B¹³, is fairly a strong electrolyte. The following equilibria exist in its aqueous solutions,

Hence, depending upon pH of the medium, RNBr^- , RNHBr , RNH_2Br^+ , RNH_2 , HOBr and H_2OBr^+ are the probable oxidising species in the aqueous solutions of BAT.

Mechanisms of oxidations: The kinetics of first order each in $[\text{BAT}]$ and $[\text{HCOOH}]$ and inverse first order in $[\text{H}^+]$ observed with HCOOH can be explained by Scheme 1 and rate law (3).

Plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{HCOOH}]$ and k_{obs} vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ (Fig. 1) gave straight lines passing through origin in accordance with rate law (4). The constant k_1 was calculated from the slope and by taking $K_a = 1.77 \times 10^{-4}$. The constant k_1 calculated from one slope was used to predict the rate constants for the variation of the other and vice versa. The rate constants predicted for the variation of $[\text{HCOOH}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ are shown in Table 3 along with the observed values. A good agreement between the two supports the proposed mechanism.

It is important to note that formic acid is not oxidised to CO_2 at $[\text{HCOOH}] \leq 0.003 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Under the reaction conditions employed with formaldehyde oxidation, HCOOH formed will be around $0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Hence the oxidation of formaldehyde to CO_2 through a consecutive mechanism is unlikely.

The observed kinetics of first order in $[\text{BAT}]_0$, zero order in $[\text{H}^+]$ and first order in $[\text{HCHO}]$, with HCHO , can be accounted by Scheme 2 and rate law (5). Formaldehyde is known to exist almost

Fig. 1. Plots of k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$ and k_{obs} vs $[HCOOH]$ for formic acid; $[HCOOH]=1.0 \times 10^{-2}$, $[BAT]=1.0 \times 10^{-2}$, $[H^+]=4.57 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm $^{-3}$.

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF CALCULATED AND OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF FORMIC ACID BY BAT

$[HCOOH]$ $\times 10^2$ mol dm $^{-3}$	$k (\times 10^4$ s $^{-1})$		$[H^+]$ $\times 10^3$ mol dm $^{-3}$	$k (\times 10^4$ s $^{-1})$	
	Calcd. ^a	Obs.		Calcd. ^a	Obs.
0.6	11.9	12.3	1.89	47.8	42.2
0.8	15.8	16.8	3.69	24.5	24.1
1.0	19.8	19.6	4.57	19.8	19.6
1.5	29.6	33.7	6.70	13.5	13.6
2.0	39.5	45.5	8.77	10.3	10.2
3.0	59.3	55.8	16.60	5.4	5.9
5.0	98.8	100.5			
10.0	197.5	182.5			

^aFrom equation (4).

completely in the hydrated form in aqueous solutions, $H_2C(OH)_2$.

Scheme 2

$$-\frac{d[BAT]}{dt} = k_2[HCHO][BAT]$$

or $k_{obs} = k_2[HCHO]$ (5)

Plot of k_{obs} vs $[HCHO]$ was linear passing through the origin in conformity with the rate law (5). The constant k_2 was calculated from the slope ($k_2 = 6.52 \times 10^{-3}$ dm 3 mol $^{-1}$ s $^{-1}$).

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